

Local Government in Germany

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Local Responsibilities and Public Services

2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Germany: An Introduction

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Urban local governments and rural local governments (hereinafter: ULGs and RLGs) traditionally have a wide range of responsibilities and, in particular, offer numerous public services. In the face of the growing urban-rural divide, these responsibilities are undergoing profound change. This change is influenced by other factors such as demographic changes and migration movements, and it can affect both the scopes of the responsibilities and the modalities of carrying them out.

While certain material responsibilities might be pushed into the background or released in their entirety (by way of a 'material privatization'), new challenges can become the focus of local government. At first glance, this applies above all to rural areas, many of which are typically affected by a significant population decline, with all its negative economic and social consequences as well as certain positive impacts, including more favorable housing conditions and a better natural environment. However, it is also the large cities and metropolitan regions that are subject to substantial segregation processes and difficulties, for example, in maintaining an efficient public transportation service, in providing sufficient housing opportunities and in dealing with the tensions following from a growing cultural and ethnic diversity. As a result, the scopes of the responsibilities carried out by ULGs and RLGs are de facto increasingly divergent and differentiated, as opposed to a de jure symmetrical approach towards responsibilities.

As regards the modalities of carrying out the responsibilities and offering the services, the changes mainly (but not exclusively) affect organizational and structural aspects. For reasons of efficiency and effectiveness, rapid changes and specific challenges may, for example, make it necessary to mobilize significant private resources in order to fulfil particularly pressing tasks through the award of public contracts or concessions as well as public private partnership undertakings. Also, local government entities might decide to provide certain public services through commercial (instead of sovereign) activities. In addition to these forms of commercialization, privatization and public private partnership, smaller local governments in particular may be forced to join forces and to cooperate with each other for the purpose of carrying out their respective responsibilities with pooled resources. Similar to their diverging substantial scopes, the different organizations and structures of responsibilities of ULGs and RLGs show more and more asymmetries.

These upheavals of local governance often necessitate policy changes – be it for the financial support of certain types of projects, be it for the (re-)definition of responsibilities, be it be it for the (re-)structuring of local government. Such structural reforms may include the reallocation of responsibilities (e.g. a transfer upon umbrella entities), the creation of new

cooperative structures (e.g. inter-municipal corporations) or – as a last resort – amalgamations of smaller local government entities (e.g. by way of a comprehensive territorial reform).⁴ In many jurisdictions, these and other policy changes are triggered and coordinated (or blocked and restricted) by powerful single local government entities or local government associations.

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⁴ See for these different structures of local government Francesco Palermo and Karl Kössler, *Comparative Federalism – Constitutional Arrangements and Case Law* (Hart Publishing 2019) 305-314.

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